

ON THE ISSUE OF WATER SAVING IN THE CULTIVATION OF GRAIN CROPS (IN THE CONDITIONS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN)

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Abstract. *This article presents the main results of a study on the use of sprinkling in the cultivation of grain crops in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.*

Keywords: *sprinkling, water resources, sowing rates and dates, grain crops, economic efficiency.*

Introduction. According to the World Water Resources Institute, Uzbekistan currently ranks 25th out of 164 countries in terms of water scarcity [1]. In the extreme conditions of Karakalpakstan, where agricultural production is impossible without irrigation, the productivity of farming depends on the level of development of irrigation and land reclamation systems, which influence the entire water use system and help mitigate the ecological situation in the region.

Traditional irrigation methods such as furrow, border, and flood irrigation do not provide uniform soil moisture, and water consumption often exceeds the required irrigation norms by 1.5–2.0 times or more. This not only reduces the efficiency of water resource use but also negatively affects the environment, causing soil erosion and leaching of pesticides and mineral fertilizers into groundwater.

For effective and rational use of available water resources, it is advisable to apply environmentally safe water-saving irrigation technologies and techniques, including sprinkler irrigation with rational irrigation norms. In this regard, the development of a resource-saving technology for cultivating high-yielding cereal crops in rice-based crop rotations, as well as the calculation of the economic efficiency of this technology under the extreme conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, is both relevant and practically significant.

Materials and Methods. The experiment was conducted on the fields of the Experimental Farm of the Scientific-Production Association of Grain and Rice of the Republic of Karakalpakstan from 2023 to 2025. The experimental plot soil is medium loam, alluvial deposits, with groundwater at a depth of 2–3 meters and a slope of $i = 0.001–0.003$. The area equipped with a sprinkler irrigation system was 2.0 hectares. The main objects of study were winter wheat, winter

triticale, and mung bean (*Vigna radiata*), as well as the application of a sprinkler system, irrigation norms, and fertilization with mineral fertilizers.

The experimental design included 16 variants: 8 variants for winter wheat + mung bean cultivation and 8 variants for winter triticale + mung bean cultivation with different sowing dates, seeding rates, and fertilizer application norms. According to the experimental scheme, winter wheat + mung bean was sown in two different periods: the first – in the second decade of September, the second – in the third decade of September, with seeding rates of 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, and 5.0 million seeds per hectare. Fertilizer application rates were as follows: N150, P100, K75; N180, P120, K90; N210, P140, K105; N180, P120, K90 kg/ha.

Winter triticale + mung bean was sown in two different periods: the first in the second decade of September and the second in the third decade of September, with seeding rates of 2.2, 2.5, 3.0, and 2.5 million seeds per hectare. Fertilizer application rates were N150, P100, K75; N180, P120, K90; N210, P140, K105; N180, P120, K90 kg/ha. In all variants, soil moisture before irrigation was maintained at 70–75% of the maximum field capacity.

Field and laboratory studies were conducted according to the methodological guidelines of VIR. Soil hydro-physical properties, irrigation timing and norms were studied following the methods of UzNIISH and SANIIR, while biometric analyses were performed according to the GSI methodology [2]. Statistical processing of the obtained data was carried out according to the method of B.A. Dospheov [3].

Results and Discussion. Field studies conducted in 2023–2025 examined irrigation methods, fertilizer application rates, sowing dates, and seeding norms for cereal crops under the soil and climatic conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Observations of irrigation and salt leaching were conducted on pilot plots. Leaching was performed at a rate of 4500 m³/ha. In variants 1, 2, 3 and 5, 6, 7, as well as 9, 10, 11 and 13, 14, 15, using sprinkler irrigation technology, the irrigation rate was 5284 (5877) m³/ha, while in variants 4, 8, 12, and 16 with traditional irrigation, it reached 6829.4 (6920) m³/ha.

During the growing season, in variants with sprinkler irrigation, winter wheat and triticale were irrigated 3–4 times with a rate of 224.1–298.4 (265–420) m³/ha, while in the control variants with traditional irrigation, irrigation was performed twice with rates of 739.6–789.8 (1170–1250) m³/ha. Analysis data indicate that the use of sprinkler irrigation for winter wheat and triticale reduced water consumption by 15–22.6% compared to traditional irrigation. To determine the economic efficiency of using sprinkler irrigation for high-yielding cereal crops with different seeding rates and fertilizer norms, all agrotechnical activities were monitored during 2023–2025, taking into account all costs for each experimental variant.

The results show that the use of scientifically based irrigation regimes, sowing dates and rates, and mineral fertilizer application with modern sprinkler systems increased the productivity per irrigated hectare. The highest yields of winter wheat were obtained in variants 3 and 7, and winter triticale in variants 11 and 15, with seeding rates of 4 million seeds/ha for wheat and 3 million seeds/ha for triticale, and fertilizer application rates of N210, P140, K105 kg/ha. Wheat yields were 62.8 (66.4) and 64.2 (67.9) c/ha, on average 8–14% higher than the control. Triticale yields were 60.2 (68.9) and 61.2 (71.2) c/ha, exceeding yields in traditionally irrigated plots by 4–7%. The relatively low yields observed in the current year were due to unfavorable weather conditions (air temperature +41–+43 °C in the first decade of May).

Moreover, according to calculations, the lowest specific water consumption per 1 c of winter wheat was in variant 7, amounting to 82 (87) m³, and for winter triticale in variant 15, 86

(83) m³, while the highest specific water consumption occurred in the control variants, 117 (123) m³ and 119 (106) m³, respectively. It should be noted that cost indicators most accurately reflect the economic efficiency of different technologies. Over two years of study, the highest profit per unit of irrigated water was recorded in variants 5, 6, 7, and 13, 14, 15, averaging 3480.9–3575.7 (2436.3–2518.4) UZS/m³ for winter wheat and 3216.9–3258.8 (2673.1–2751.0) UZS/m³ for winter triticale. Profit growth compared to the previous year was due solely to an increase in grain selling prices.

The total cost of the sprinkler irrigation system installed on the experimental plot was 59,500 thousand UZS (excluding expenses for sedimentation tanks, filters, and pipelines), or an average of 29,750 thousand UZS per hectare. Based on calculations under the current crop yields of winter wheat and triticale, the payback period of the sprinkler system is estimated at 5 years. If the profit from cultivating a second crop – mung bean – is included, the payback period decreases to approximately 3 years (assuming that one-third of the income from crop sales is used to cover the cost of the irrigation system).

Thus, the obtained results demonstrate the high efficiency of cultivating winter wheat and winter triticale using scientifically justified irrigation regimes with modern sprinkler systems under the extreme conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. This resource-saving cultivation technology not only allows for water and seed savings but also ensures higher crop yields and increased profits.

Conclusion. Based on the results of the study conducted in 2023–2025, the following conclusions can be drawn:

The use of sprinkler irrigation for winter wheat and triticale allowed a reduction in water consumption by 15–22.6%. The highest yields and profits of cereal crops were obtained in variants with sprinkler irrigation, fertilizer application rates of N210, P140, K105, and seeding rates of 3 million seeds/ha for winter triticale and 4 million seeds/ha for winter wheat, sown in the third decade of September. The payback period of the sprinkler irrigation system at current crop yields is on average 5 years; taking into account the cultivation of a second crop – mung bean – the payback period is reduced to approximately 3 years.

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